

SEARCHING ON HETEROGENEOUS AND DECENTRALIZED DATA: A SHORT REVIEW

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Abstract

Within the last few years, the amount of recorded data has increased significantly. Information is collected from a wide variety of areas, such as healthcare, autonomous driving, or e-commerce. In addition, the recorded data is usually not stored centrally, but is rather distributed across various decentralized infrastructures. This complicates searching for the desired data. Several papers have already been published that discuss approaches for finding the requested information within heterogeneous and decentralized data architectures. To highlight the similarities and differences between the various approaches, this paper conducts an integrative literature review on search architectures that deal with heterogeneous and decentralized data. This is done by decomposing existing architectures in different layers: It was found that the identified architectures first abstract from the original technologies of the heterogeneous data sources, and then use different indexing strategies in combination with a search algorithm to find and present the queried information.

INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly networked world, the value of data as a common good has significantly increased. New technologies and achievements in science and industry rely on data-driven workflows more than ever. However, as the amount of publicly available data is continuously growing, finding accurate pieces of information in large, distributed, or decentralized infrastructures has become a problem. This problem can not only be observed in the human-readable part of the internet, but is also present for publicly available databases, multi-media content or file repositories [1]. With the increased availability of Big Data in several areas in research and economy, being able to find the right sets of data has become more and more relevant for success. In this context, initiatives like the Open Search Foundation aim at providing open and independent approaches for fulfilling these tasks [2]. These approaches could play an important role for future developments and should not only deal with classical web data, but also with data from a variety of heterogeneous data sources. Nevertheless, web search and search on heterogeneous data sources is not contradictory: Common approaches combine both types of data, to provide intelligent query functionalities that rely on knowledge representations and intelligent indexes generated from heterogeneous data (cf. [3], [4]).

More openly developed search approaches rely on decentralizing the utilized infrastructure and incoming processing tasks to strengthen overall trust and to equally

distribute processing power. Analogously, data from heterogeneous data sources can also often be found in decentralized structures. This means, that the data is not stored in a central location like, e.g., a data lake, but is distributed to different sources, typically controlled by different providers, and based on different technologies. This introduces new challenges to the design of search systems.

In this paper, we present the challenges of searching on heterogeneous and decentral data sources in comparison to conventional web search. Furthermore, a short integrative literature is conducted and common architectures for solving the identified challenges are examined on four different architectural levels.

SEARCH ON HETEROGENEOUS DATA

Conventional web search architectures typically start with a crawler, that crawls web pages and saves them in a local copy with a pre-defined format (crawl dump) that is then processed by an indexer. The indexer analyses the saved data and maps possible search terms to data points in the crawl dump: this creates the index. Finally, a search algorithm is used, that takes input from a user of the search engine and uses the index to find search results (cf. Figure 1). These elements typically differ in their specific realization but can most often be found in conventional search engines. [5]

Figure 1: Classical Web Search Engine Architecture (cf. [5])

On the first sight, this process seems easily adaptable to use-cases with other types of data. However, some pre-conditions are required here, so that the architecture cannot be transferred to heterogeneous data sources without further effort: To start with, the web crawler makes use of the standardization of web content accessibility: The Hyper-Text Transfer Protocol (HTTP) is supported by any website, so that the crawler can access web-content in a standardized way [6]. When considering heterogeneous data sources, this is one of the first obstacles: A common interface to access arbitrary data sources cannot be assumed. Rather, the data sources come in a variety of different technologies, and different types of access-policies. Furthermore, it may not always make sense to create a complete local copy of available data sources, as there is no homogeneous data structure that could manage these and make them easily indexable as it can be done with

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HTML documents. Like web-crawlers, which sometimes only store parts of the web data (e.g., filtering out image or video data) or meta-data, storing only processed information about the heterogeneous data sources can be a solution to this problem [7]. After that, web search engines profit from the fact, that most of their indexed content is given in standardized formats (html, xml, etc.) that are known before runtime [6]. These formats are then parsed by the indexer, which usually extracts the human readable text and generates keywords and metadata that map to the desired sections of the crawl dump [8]. As the formats of the data from heterogeneous data sources are not known before runtime, it is much harder to find suitable indexing strategies. Additionally, as heterogeneous data may also include non-human-readable information, the question arises if a simple keyword search is effective in such a case [9]. Another important difference is that it cannot be assumed, that heterogeneous data is linked in any way: Web crawlers can find web pages by following URLs and continuously extend their knowledge about areas of the public internet, which is typically not possible in multiple heterogeneous data sources. This can also become a problem, when utilizing metrics like “number of web pages referring to a specific web page” for search ranking algorithms, as it is often done in web search engines [10].

This problem of searching in heterogeneous and decentralised data has already been discussed in several scientific publications. However, to our best knowledge, there has been almost no effort to review the literature regarding the presented search architectures. The only work in this area, that could be identified was a paper by Wang et al. [11], who discuss the problem specifically from the perspective of search queries. Nevertheless, their work is restricted to the application in data spaces and does not discuss the architectural principles behind the different types of queries.

REVIEW OF SEARCH ARCHITECTURES

To analyse common search architectures that deal with

heterogeneous and decentral data, we conduct an integrative literature review: We manually search Elsevier Scopus and Google Scholar (cf. [12]) for the following search term, based on the discussion in the previous section:

(indexing OR search) AND (heterogeneous data OR data architecture OR unstructured data OR decentral)

To limit the large amount of search results, we only consider the 160 search results ranked most relevant for both search engines, leading to a total of 320 search results that are considered within this review. For our review, only publications were considered, that (1) are related to search in data, (2) either deal with heterogeneous data or decentral organization of data and (3) present an architecture. To identify publications that meet these criteria, out of the 320 search results, 113 were selected for further consideration based on their title. Then, after scanning their abstracts, 63 papers were identified, which were examined completely. Finally, and without duplicates, 33 papers were found, that fulfil the defined criteria.

In summary, most of the analysed architectures are based on the presence of heterogeneous data sources, that can contain structured, semi-structured or unstructured data. Secondly, some type of technology abstraction layer for the actual data sources is implemented to enable a unified access to them. As already stated, crawling components usually are not part of search architectures for heterogeneous data sources. Also, the understanding of an indexing strategy is extended to more generic representations than keyword indices. Even though several architectures provide keyword indexing, others completely rely on creating ontologies or other mappings. Several architectures can also deal with basic decentralization of data sources implicitly by their design, as they connect each data source individually to the rest of the system. The following section provides a detailed analysis of the different components in search architectures that deal with heterogeneous or decentralized data. An abstract model of

Figure 2: Architectural Framework for Search in Heterogeneous Data Sources.

these architectures is depicted in Figure 2: Starting with data sources that should be indexed, a technology abstraction layer is introduced to provide unified access. This layer is then used to provide the required data for an indexing strategy. Finally, results of the indexing strategy can be accessed by the search algorithm, which in combination with an interface represents the search service to a user. The following sub-sections present more details of the single components.

(Heterogeneous) Data Sources

The data sources represent the basis of most architecture. Heterogeneous data source can contain structured data in databases (e.g., PostgreSQL, MySQL, MongoDB), semi-structured data (e.g., json, XML) or unstructured data (e.g., text files, images, video data). For many use-cases, this data is often not organized in a centrally controlled structure, but is often distributed to different single data providers, that also use different data models and access policies. Many of the identified search architectures can deal with arbitrary types of data sources. However, this requires manual integration procedures most of the time. On the other hand, some of the identified architectures are focused on specific types of heterogeneous data and therefore are often able to provide a more precise search functionality for the respective type of data. For example in [13] and [14], the authors specifically focus on multimedia data. Also, there are many approaches that rely on textual representation of information (e.g., [15] or [16]) as this can be very helpful for keyword-based search approaches. Lastly, other approaches, such as [17], are closer to common web-search approaches and base their architecture on data sources that are available on the web.

Abstraction of Technologies

When creating an index on heterogeneous data, the challenge lies in making the individual data source accessible for the application of an indexing strategy. In contrast to typical web indexing, the structure in which the data is stored is not uniform. However, indexing strategies need to know in which representation they will find the individual data sources that have to be indexed. Therefore, it is not directly possible to execute a single indexing strategy on arbitrary data sources. For this purpose, an abstraction from the respective structure of the heterogeneous data sources into a uniform structure must be carried out first. We model this abstraction in our generalized architecture as “connectors” (cf. Figure 2). The identified architectures differ in the realization of connectors and can be divided into two classes: Either the data source technology is abstracted to translate search requests to the native technology of the data source and execute them on the data source (as e.g. in [18], [19] or [20]) or to provide access to the data itself in such a way that an index or similar (external) data structures can be created, which is later used for searching (as e.g. in [21], [22] or [23]). In the second case, there are also some approaches like [24] or [25] in which the complete set of data is analysed and transformed to a unified representation, which is then

used exclusively for search. It also must be noted that the connectors are not always a standalone component, but often part of indexing strategies or query translation components.

Indexing Strategies

With technological abstraction, the problem of syntactic heterogeneity can be solved, at least for the functionalities that are offered by the connectors. However, the problem of semantic heterogeneity of the data sources and differences in the characteristics of their data remains. The main differences in the identified search architecture could be found in the indexing strategies. Specific implementations of these also depend on the use-case of a search algorithm: Simple keyword-based search algorithms require different indexing strategies than more complex search algorithms, that may accept a variety of additional parameters or even structured queries. As more precise indexing also requires higher levels of data source integration and therefore higher effort and the requirements can be very different, we refer to the term *indexing strategy* as the process of generating a knowledge representation for searching. The following indexing strategies could be identified in the reviewed literature:

Graph-based indexing strategies. These strategies mainly rely on the representation of knowledge about the heterogeneous data sources in graphs. Most commonly, the nodes in these graphs represent entities or attributes in the data, while edges are data-specific relationships [24], [25], [25]. Often, the Resource Description Framework (RDF) is used to encode this information (e.g. in [20] or [25]). Search algorithms can then exploit relations in the graph for search terms that can be associated with specific nodes in the graph or answer structured queries in graph querying languages. Another approach is presented by [21], who use graphs to model the similarity of keywords in the data to find data entities, that match to given search keywords. A similar utilization of graphs was found in [27], who use a graph data structure that represents semantic correlations of data objects as a base for their search algorithm.

Vector space indexing strategies. Vector space indexing strategies are based on an algebraic model to assess the relevance of possible search results in relation to the search query and is realized by indexing documents as vectors in a vector space [15]. In this way, each dataset can be represented as a vector in the index, in which every entry represents the importance of a specific keyword in the associated dataset [16]. Finally, the query is also represented in the vector space and a similarity measure is used to find the closest dataset representations in the vector space [28]. Apart from the specific vector representation schema and the similarity measure, the identified approaches did not differ significantly in their realization of this indexing strategy.

Inverted list indices. One of the most common indexing strategies that was found, was using inverted list indices to index heterogeneous data sources. These indices

typically consist of a mapping of possible search keywords to lists of datasets that are related to these keywords [29]. Keywords for the inverted list can, for example, be extracted from text-based data, or available metadata. Realizations of this strategy differ in how the indices deal with the presence of multiple data sources. For instance, [22] implement a concept with local indices for each data source, which are connected by a global index, that maps search keywords to the local indices. However, most of the time, the specific implementation of inverted indices is not discussed in detail in the reviewed literature. Often, this task is outsourced to external libraries, such as Apache Lucene [30], [23], [31].

Ontology-based strategies. Ontologies are a common concept to represent semantic knowledge in a formal way, e.g., by defining concepts, relations, instances, types or other entities and interconnecting them. In searching, ontologies are often used to map general user queries to specific queries, that can be answered by specific data sources, by utilizing semantic knowledge about the similarity of concepts in the user query and the heterogeneous data sources [32], [33]. Ontologies can even be used to provide structured query interfaces (such as SQL) for multiple heterogeneous data sources [34]. Apart from that, ontologies in the search context may also be used to enhance user queries with additional information such as synonyms [35], [36], to transform user queries of geographical terms to machine-readable geographic representations (for instance, to translate place names to coordinates)[37] or simply to provide a common data model, which has to be adopted by the data sources, before they can be searched [38].

Other strategies. Finally, some other strategies could be identified that did not match the previously introduced categories. [18] and [19] both present a custom translation model, that transforms user queries to native query interfaces of the data sources without ontologies. [39] also implement such a strategy and refer to this type of query translation as “wrapper” or “mediator” architecture. [40] use Distributed Hash Tables (DHT) to index data files. This works by calculating hashes for possible queries to any data set and then lookup the hashes of user queries in the index. To improve the chance to find matching datasets with a single query, similar queries are derived from the original query and also executed. Similarly, [41] also use DHTs for indexing. In [14], machine-learning is utilized to learn hash-functions that project image or text into a common representation, which can later be used to find search results that are related with an image or text query. Finally, [42] propose a framework, which is based on ElasticSearch*, a search and analytics engine which can flexibly be configured to index different types of data.

Search Service

How a search query is executed clearly depends on the underlying indexing strategy and is often evident. For instance, inverted lists directly provide a mapping from a

query to a possible search result. Graph-based indexing strategies use graph querying languages or graph traversal, vector space indices use a similarity measure and ontologies are used to enhance the query itself or map the query to a native query interface. However, users of a search engine usually do not want to see all available search results, but the top-k results that are most relevant [25]. Typical search ranking algorithms such as the famous PageRank algorithm, utilize an inverted text index for keyword search to obtain possible search results and then order them by utilizing a ranking algorithm (cf. [10]). In heterogeneous data sources, ranking search results is also of high interest, but not as easy as in the web search scenario due to their inhomogeneities [43]. There are several different criteria, that can be utilized to rank these search results. They include semantic distance between datasets and search query, number of references to the data set (or similar datasets) [38], similarity ([15], [28], [36]), popularity or user preferences [42], structural properties in graph-indices ([24], [26]) or geographical distances for spatial queries [37]. However, methods for ranking search results from heterogeneous data sources were only discussed by a smaller amount of the identified papers.

Finally, depending on the implemented algorithm, the presentation of the search results also has to be considered in the process of developing search architectures. Especially when visualizing the heterogeneous results for human users, other methods than just displaying a list of search results including their descriptions may be more appropriate. Nevertheless, only a fraction of the identified papers discussed this area at all. Some approaches present their search results as graphs or diagrams [22],[24],[25], others only provide a textual list of results [34], [13].

Decentralization

As heterogeneous data sources are often found in the context of decentralization, this is an important part of search architectures, especially in the context of open search approaches. In the worst-case, each source of data is managed separately with its own connector. On the other hand, many connectors can be an advantage when it comes to data sovereignty: The provider of a data source can have full control over the respective connector and does not have to allow complete and uncontrolled access to the data. This also moves the responsibility and obligations to a wider set of institutions and avoids centrally controlled infrastructures, which can be a problem for independent search approaches (cf. [44]). The same principle can be applied on the index level (see also Figure 2): There may not be a single index for all available data sources: Both duplicating indices and partitioning indices based on specific parameters are options. However, if complete coverage for searching is required, the search algorithm needs access to all available data in indices. In general, the problem of centrally managed data sources and the organisational aspects were not directly covered by any of the identified approaches. Some of the proposed architectures may still be applicable in these cases, but

* <https://www.elastic.co/de/elasticsearch/>

especially those, who outsource query execution to the data sources or aggregate large amounts of data from the sources in a central infrastructure may lead to organizational problems.

CONCLUSION

To assess the current state-of-the-art in searching heterogeneous and decentralized data sources, we conducted an integrative literature review in this paper. It could be shown that searching on decentralized and heterogeneous data sources brings some difficulties in contrast to traditional web search approaches. Distributed data sources differ not only in terms of their content and structures but also within their used technologies and organisational aspects. Furthermore, the results of our review lead to an overview of the important architectural layers and their possible realizations. With the approach of Big Data in nearly any sector of today's economy and research activities, it seems very important, that besides web data, other data sources can also be included in search architectures. Therefore, we expect research that deals with decentralization aspects, both on the technical and organisational level, to be growing in relevance, especially in the context of open search approaches.

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